

THE ROLE OF CIVIC EDUCATION IN THE FORMATION OF NATION CHARACTERS, AS EDUCATION INTRODUCTION TO THE STATE

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Abstract

The existence of citizenship education is very important in forming human beings with character and have a strong state defense attitude, but seeing from the material that is abundant but not balanced with adequate time allocation, of course this will have an inadequacy and not yet embedded love and defense A high country, so efforts need to be made so that this lecture is not just a symbol, but it is hoped that it can be a problem solving of the existing problems. the hope of implementing the values of the nation's ideological values must always be mobilized in echoing from kindergartens to tertiary institutions, the phenomenon that there is citizenship education with existing material content is thought to have not been able to instill a sense of nationalism and state defense The existence of Citizenship Education has a very important role and function in shaping the behavior of Indonesian students by incorporating it into the education system they hold, it is hoped that its citizens will become smart citizens and good citizens who know and realize fully their rights as citizens, as well as knowing and being fully responsible for their obligations towards the safety of their nation and country. Citizenship Education (PKn) developed in Indonesia should also be able to rediscover the relevance of the fundamental values of society with rapidly changing social dynamics. By teaching Civics, it should not only be a matter of cognitive issues, but must provide a moral and social action touch. As a preliminary education, the defense of citizenship education plays a very strategic role in efforts to shape the nation's character.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Citizenship education plays an important role for the State in order to prepare intelligent, responsible and know their own citizens. The terminology of this course is different in every country that mentions civic education, citizenship education, and some even call democracy education Based on the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education system and the Decree of the Director General of Higher Education Ministry of National Education Number 43 / DIKTI / Kep / 2006 concerning Implementation Signposts for Personality Development courses in universities, civic education is a subject must be given in all faculties and all departments throughout universities in the archipelago The citizenship education that was developed certainly cannot be separated from its basis, namely Pancasila which is used as a source of all sources of law in our country As stated (Mansoer, 2005) the philosophy of Pancasila contains the contents of Indonesia's national identity and the content of the meaning of the preliminary education of State defense Based on the fact, the awareness of the importance of the rights and obligations of citizens as well as the awareness of democracy must always be fostered and implemented in real life, in family life, in a nation and state society.

In line with these expectations, of course the hope of implementing the values of the nation's ideology must always be mobilized in echoing from kindergartens to universities, the

phenomenon that there is citizenship education with material content that is now thought to have not been able to instill a sense of nationalism and a sense of national defense.

For this reason, this article limits the discussion on the role of civic education / civic education in the formation of national character as part of the preliminary education to defend the state. The purpose of this writing is as expected to provide both theoretical and practical benefits that are useful for the development of knowledge and provide input to stakeholders to make policies.

1. The results of this academic study will certainly be useful in enriching the education discipline more specifically contributing to the development of learning methods.
2. Practically the results of this study are useful for lecturers to further improve competence in lectures on civic education

2. EXISTENCE OF CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PERSONALITY

2.1 CIVIC EDUCATION

Citizenship education in universities is presented with separate lectures separated from Pancasila education, basically the same as civic education, namely how to make good citizenship. Citizenship Education is an effort to equip students with basic knowledge and abilities regarding the relationship between citizens and the state to become citizens that can be relied upon by the nation and the state. Successful Citizenship Education will produce a mental attitude that is intelligent and full of responsibility from students through Citizenship Education, citizens of the Republic of Indonesia are expected to be able to understand, analyze and answer the problems faced by society, the nation and the country on an ongoing basis and be consistent with their national ideals and goals as outlined in the opening of the 1945 Constitution. In filling independence and facing globalization, every citizen of the Republic of Indonesia in general and students in particular must remain on their identity who are patriotic and patriotic in the non-physical struggle in accordance with their respective professions in all aspects of life.

Citizenship Education is all things related to citizens both empirical and non-empirical, in the form of insight, attitudes and behavior of citizens in the Republic of Indonesia. Citizenship Education has a very important role and function in shaping the behavior of Indonesian students by including them in the education system they hold, it is hoped that their citizens will become smart citizens and good citizens who know and are fully aware of their rights as citizens, as well as knowing and being fully responsible for their obligations towards the safety of their nation and country. Thus the granting of Citizenship Education will give birth to citizens who have high souls and patriotism and nationalism. In general, civic education carried out by various countries aims and aims so that the citizens of the nation re-explore the basic values, history and future of the nation in accordance with the most fundamental values (basic state) adopted by the nation that concerned. In line with this fact, the essence of Civics which is one part of personality courses must prioritize the affective aspects among students. The philosophical foundation and hope above, then need to find its relevance to the conditions and challenges of real life in society, so that Citizenship Education is able to contribute positively to solving social problems that are being faced by a nation or society. Therefore, whatever form of Citizenship Education developed in various nations, it is very necessary to develop the fundamental values of the nation (society) in accordance with the dynamics of social change, so that the foundational values find their relevance to contribute significantly to the problems of society, the nation. Citizenship (PKn) developed in Indonesia should also be able to rediscover the relevance of the fundamental values

of society with rapidly changing social dynamics. By teaching Civics, it should not only be a matter of cognitive issues, but must provide a moral and social action touch.

This moral and social action touch must receive greater attention, so that the teaching of Civics is able to reach its goals and objectives, namely to shape students into good and responsible citizens.

Indeed, when the founder of the Republic stipulated Article 31 paragraph (2) of the 1945 Constitution which obliged "the Government to strive for and administer a national teaching system", it was intended that education was designed, especially school education, to give birth to Indonesian citizens who supported the development of an intelligent nation of life. In other words, national education is essentially citizenship education in order to produce good quality Indonesian citizens in disciplines, both social discipline and national discipline, in the work ethic, in work productivity, in intellectual ability, professional / or vocational ability, in a sense of community responsibility nationality and humanity, as well as morality, character and personality. Quality human beings like this are expected to be produced by the education process and school Citizenship Education is developed in education in higher education because it is a conscious effort to prepare students through guidance and / or training activities in order to develop or foster awareness, love, loyalty and courage to sacrifice in order to defend the nation and country. As well as aiming for the nation's citizens to explore the basic values, history and future of the nation in accordance with the values of the pali

2.2 THE EXISTENCE OF CITIZENSHIP EDUCATION FORMS THE NATION'S PERSONALITY

In the opinion of the author the existence of citizenship education is very important in shaping human beings who have character and have a strong state defense attitude, but seeing from the material that is numerous but not balanced with adequate time allocation, of course this will have an inadequate impact and not yet embedded high love and defense of the State, so efforts need to be made so that this lecture is not just a symbol but it is hoped that it can be a problem solving of every problem that exists, because as we know the character of the nation which has begun to be eroded by the culture of the outside culture, waning sense of solidarity among others, the development of racism, understanding radicalism.

To take care of all these problems is certainly not as easy as turning the palm of the hand, the reform era marked by the fall of the new order government is our embryo to restore the implementation of the 1945 constitution purely and consistently, one of which is safely amended to the 1945 Constitution.

Aside from that, Pancasila and citizenship education as a preliminary education for martial arts need to be instilled from an early age, up to college, by integrating preliminary education to defend the country with compulsory military practice, so here students do not study theory theory but are accompanied by practice and mental formation the tough one. As a real example, holding a flag ceremony every month, wearing costumes that show our identity like batik and they are also taught with marching physical exercises.

Intense ideas carried out by the government through the four pillars of nationality are programs that can maintain the integrity of the nation in this increasingly competitive era, the value of noble values need to be made as a reference and guidance for every citizen in the life of nation and state.

1. Pancasila
2. Bhineka Tunggal ika
3. The 1945 Constitution
4. The Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia

Every nation has its identity. By understanding the nation's identity, it is expected to understand the national identity so as to foster pride as a nation. In this discussion, certainly cannot ignore the discussion of past and present conditions, between ideality and reality and between the *das Sollen* and *das Sein*.

The character comes from the Latin "karakter, kharassein or kharax", in French "caractere" in English "character. In the broadest sense of character means the nature of psychology, character, character, character, character that distinguishes someone from others (National Team Lecturer for Citizenship Education, 2011: 67). Thus the character of the nation can be interpreted as a typical Indonesian character or character that distinguishes the Indonesian nation from other nations.

According to Max Weber (quoted by Darmaputra, 1988: 3) the best way to understand a society is to understand the behavior of its members. And the way to understand the behavior of members is to understand their culture that is their system of meaning. Humans are creatures who always seek continuous meaning for all their actions. The meaning is always the orientation of human actions whether consciously or not. Humans also seek and try to explain 'logic' of the social behavior of certain communities through their own culture. In developing societies or Third World societies, generally face three main problems namely nation-building, political stability and economic development. Nation-building is a problem that relates to the inheritance of the past, how diverse communities try to build shared unity. Political stability is a problem related to the current reality of the threat of disintegration. While the problem of economic development is a problem related to the future, namely (in the Indonesian context) a just and prosperous society (Darmaputra, 1988: 5).

We have no doubt about the existence of Pancasila as a fundamental norm, the Pancasila that was born from a long formulation by the founding father has succeeded in uniting the values of life that grow and develop in the middle of Indonesian society, from Sabang to Merauke. Diversity as the strength of the Indonesian Nation which must always be maintained Diversity should we understand as a unifying force of a nation whose existence cannot be denied. Diversity must also be interpreted by the community through understanding multiculturalism based on the power of spirituality. The power of spirituality here means that society sees that difference as a unifying diversity, accepting difference as a force not as a threat or interference. All existing cultures, religions & tribes remain in their respective forms, what unites is the sense of nationalism of pride as an Indonesian nation that has hundreds of cultures, customs, customs.

Diversity is a unifying pillar of the nation that must be viewed with pride, pride because we can be separated from narrow primordialism which considers race, adat, other religions to be inferior / worse than personal property. The compartmentalization of this element of society is the fruit of the Dutch colonial era that used the war tactic "devide et impera".

The attitude and view of the narrow primordiariness will bring Indonesia to the destruction & disintegration of the nation. Horizontal conflict (between communities) often occurs due to trivial & trivial matters, to bring problems to SARA. Sad & apprehensive for a country the size of Indonesia which had been independent 73 years ago it was always compartmentalizing the elements of society to the smallest things. Unity in Diversity It cannot be considered merely a slogan, but it is lived in life, kept in the heart of every Indonesian citizen to maintain the unity of the state. In principle, the slogan of the Indonesian people has a very important meaning, namely tolerance and unity. First, tolerance can dissolve differences into unity so that there are no divisions or conflicts. Second, Unity is something that must be done in realizing unity and unity of various races, tribes, and religions The 1945 Constitution of the 1945 Constitution is interpreted as a written Constitution or a basic charter which contains the principle that contains norms for the implementation of state government.

3. CONCLUSION

From the discussion above we can conclude that in general Understanding Citizenship Education in Higher Education is one of the efforts to revive the national spirit of the younger generation, especially students, in facing the influence of globalization and to strengthen awareness of defending the country. which is very strategic in the effort to form the character of the nation, character or character can only be formed and developed through the educational process, it is not possible with teaching. The aim of Understanding Citizenship Education in Higher Education is to foster awareness of basic obligations in the defense of the state with a nation and state that has an integral comprehensive mindset.

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